

Ozone (2B) Instrument Description

Last updated 4 Jan 2023

Ozone measurements are made by the FAAM Airborne Laboratory using a dual beam UV absorption photometer, specifically a 2B Technologies model 205 (rackmount, s/n 1034DB). This instrument has been flown since 2011, and is operated as shown in the flow diagram below.

Following recommendations from 2B Technologies to improve precision for 2 sec data acquisition rates, the photometer motherboard and firmware were upgraded to version 'I' and a new UV lamp block fitted in Oct 2020.

The instrument sample flow rate is approximately 2.5 SLPM, provided by its internal sampling pump.

An 5 μm PTFE particulate membrane, held in an external in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4), protects the photometer's internal optics from potential contamination.

Note that the I/Io cell measurement cycle is 2 sec; although data submitted in the core_faam_yyyymmdd_v004_rx_cxxx_1hz.nc data files is logged at 1 Hz, the true measurement rate is ~ 0.5 Hz.

Sample inlet and instrument response

From 2012 to 2021, a rear-ward facing 1/2" OD stainless steel (SS) tube, mounted on a blank BAe-146 aircraft Aluminium window, served as an ozone inlet. The SS tube ID was lined with a 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube, to accommodate simultaneous atmospheric sampling of ozone, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide.

Since 2021, a new pressure-building trace gas inlet has replaced the rear-ward facing inlet. This inlet was initially designed by Richard J. McLaughlin, an instrument design and fabrication specialist at NOAA's Chemical Sciences Division, for NASA's Douglas DC8 (e.g. ATom-2 missions) and NOAA's Lockheed WP-3D Orion aircrafts. The inlet design was first adapted to interface with our aircraft windows by Chris Reed at FAAM in 2019, for use as a fast NOx measurements inlet.

The new core chemistry McLaughlin inlet is located on starboard windows no. 11 or 12 depending on the cabin configuration (i.e. ~12 to 13 m from the nose of the aircraft). The picture below illustrates the pylon/shroud inlet mounted on window no. 11 (nose of aircraft to the RHS of picture).

Two of the three inlet internal ports within the pylon are lined with 1/4" OD PFA Teflon tubes, then teed to a single 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube.

Ambient air is drawn into the aircraft cabin through the 3/8" OD Teflon tube using an all-PTFE Teflon double-headed sample pump (KNF part no. N834.3 FTE). The sample flow (~25 SLPM near surface, degrading to ~ 7 SLPM at 35000') passes through a two-way, normally open, electro-solenoid all-PFA valve (eValve5, Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-2414-213), used to seal the inlet during pre-flight preparations.

The operation of the KNF sample pump and eValve 5 is automated by the aircraft weight-on-wheels signal; ambient air sampling starts as soon as the aircraft is airborne. This

arrangement minimises instrument inlet contamination by airfield polluted air, such as during engines start with aircraft parked on stand, or while taxiing for take-off and after landing.

The air sample is transferred to a 3/8" to 1/4" Teflon tee piece (Entegris/Galtek part no part# UT4-6-4N); a short length 1/4" od Teflon tubing connects the tee piece to the ozone instrument inlet particulate filter.

The excess flow provided by the KNF sample pump is directed to a PFA Teflon buffer volume (PFAVOL) constructed out of three 1 1/2" MNPT 120 mL column segments (Savillex part no. 500-120-02), 3/8" OD tube port closures (Savillex part no. 600-058-19), and female connectors (Savillex part no. 730-0502). The buffer volume is used to dampen oscillating flow effects caused by the KNF sample pump (double diaphragm pressure pulses).

An ozone instrument zero can be performed pre- and post-flight using an external 500 mL capacity scrubber cartridge (Cole Parmer part no. 01418-50) equipped with in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4) and 5 μ m PTFE membrane. This scrubber cartridge is half-filled with potassium permanganate coated alumina spheres (Sofnofil, from Molecular Products Ltd), and activated charcoal, for the removal of NO_x, Ozone and SO₂. During the preparatory phase on the ground, the KNF sample pump is powered off, cabin air can pass through this scrubber cartridge by actuating the three-way electro-solenoid eValve 6 (Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-3414-213), so ozone-scrubbed cabin air can be sampled by the ozone photometer.

During flight, the overflow from the KNF sample pump is constantly monitored by a microbridge mass airflow sensor (MFM, Honeywell model AWM5104VN, 0-20 SLPM), to ensure cabin air is not inadvertently sampled, especially when the inlet pumping performance decreases while approaching our flight ceiling altitude (30000-35000 feet).

The above sampling inlet arrangement enables the ozone photometer to work within its operating pressure limits, with its inlet pressure effectively following the aircraft cabin pressure.

Based on the current inlet configuration, the instrument lag time is estimated to be $\sim 2 \pm 1$ sec based on comparison of 1 Hz ozone and 10 Hz nitric oxide measurements (ozone titration assessment in ship plumes during the ACRUISE1 2019 missions). Please note that no correction for lag time has been applied to our submitted data timestamps.

Calibration and measurement traceability

FAAM's ozone photometer model 205 is calibrated at least yearly against an ozone primary standard (Thermo Scientific model 49i-PS, s/n 0703820527) maintained by the University of York's [COZI laboratory](#), part of the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories. This primary standard ensures the traceability of ozone photometers operated by ground-based and airborne facilities of the National Centre for Atmospheric Science to NIST/NPL.

FAAM's ozone photometers are generally calibrated over the range 0-500 ppb, to cover the high ozone concentrations encountered at high altitudes in stratospheric influenced air.

The photometer is "zeroed" during pre-flights (see previous section) to check the ozone measurements comply with the expected instrumental precision (<1 ppb for 10 second averages).

FAAM operates an ozone calibration source (2B Technologies model 306, s/n 238). This calibration source was calibrated against the COZI laboratory ozone primary standard on 24 August 2021 using 2B Technologies' Technical Note No 016 (see calibration report in Appendix). The model 306 'Z' and 'S' calibration parameters were found in excellent agreement with pre-calibration values, 1 ppb for 'Z' and 1% for 'S', well within our measurements uncertainty.

For the ACRUISE-2 and ACRUISE-3 missions, our model 205 photometer was calibrated at FAAM against our model 306 calibration source on 4 August 2021, over the concentration range 0-300 ppb. The calibration curve obtained for this transfer standard confirms excellent linearity over the measurement range.

Measurement uncertainty

The uncertainty of ACRUISE-2 and ACRUISE-3 ozone measurements can be estimated from the calibration of FAAM's ozone calibration source (see Appendix), namely for amount fractions greater than 100 nmol/mol: $\pm 3\%$ of value, and for amount fractions between 0 and 100 nmol/mol: ± 3 nmol/mol.

A further source of uncertainty was quantified after the ACRUISE-1 2019 missions and reported in Jake Vallow's Master of Chemistry thesis (April 2021). This FAAM study of the impact of water vapour and pressure on the accuracy of our model 205 suggests an additional ± 2 nmol/mol uncertainty. This extra uncertainty however mainly affects ozone measurements conducted in highly variable water vapour regimes (deep ascent/descent within free troposphere) which are uncharacteristic of ACRUISE missions, which science surveys focussed mainly on the marine boundary layer.

Note that the impact of differential pressure and water vapour on the 2B Technologies photometers equipped with Dewline Nafion water exchange membranes is a known issue, which has been addressed and reported by other airborne research groups (e.g. Hintsa et al, 2021).

References

Eric J. Hintsa et al, UAS Chromatograph for Atmospheric Trace Species (UCATS) – a versatile instrument for trace gas measurements on airborne platforms, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 6795–6819, 2021 (doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-6795-2021)

Appendix

24 August 2021 Calibration Report for FAAM's 2B Technologies model 306 s/n 238 ozone calibration source, Katie Read, COZI-Lab, WACL, NCAS/AMOF, University of York

Certificate of calibration

For: Dr Stéphane Bauguitte
Chemistry Specialist
FAAM
Cranfield University
Bedford
MK430AL
United Kingdom

Date: 24th August 2021

Serial Number of Instrument: #238

Results: **Model 306 O3 nmol/mol = 1.2426 NCAS COZI O3 nmol/mol -0.8045 nmol/mol**

Uncertainty at amount fractions greater than 100 nmol/mol = $\pm 3\%$ of value. Uncertainty at amount fractions between 0 and 100 nmol/mol = 3nmol/mol.

Carried out by: Dr Katie Read
NCAS Scientist
University of York
York, UK

Signed:

Authorised by: Dr Katie Read
NCAS Scientist
University of York
York, UK

Signed:

Reference to NIST Scale

The NCAS Primary Standard (TE49i) #0703820527 is calibrated annually at the National Physical Laboratory against the NIST Standard Reference Photometer SRP 20, quality assured and controlled by independent audit procedures. The calibration performed relates the output from the NCAS TE49i analyser front panel to the ozone amount fractions determined by the SRP.

The most recent NPL calibration (3rd December 2020) of the NCAS Primary Standard reported: -

TE49i nmol/mol = 0.975 SRP20 nmol/mol + 0.5 nmol/mol

The span was noticed by NPL to be in error so was adjusted back from 0.991 to 1.011 to give a new calibration of:

TE49i nmol/mol = 0.995 SRP20 nmol/mol + 0.5 nmol/mol

Measurement procedure

The core COZI instrument was calibrated using the NCAS Primary Standard (TE49i). The results are below:

The calibration of the model 306 was carried out according to the procedure outlined in Technical note No. 016. Z and S were set to 0 and 1 respectively. The original values were Z= +2, S = 0.81.

The zero data is presented below, the zero was evaluated as 0 ppb target, the ozone lamp turned off. The mean value was 0.11 ppbV.

Three calibrations were carried out and a summary of the third is detailed below.

2b 306 output nmol/mol = **m** COZI O3 49C Ozone in nmol/mol + **c**

where: **m** is the gradient determined as the ratio of the core instrument reading for ozone to the 2b 306 output for ozone, **c** is the intercept expressed in nmol/mol.

Results

Ozone 49C reading (nmol/mol)	2b O3 (nmol/mol)	Standard deviation (nmol/mol)
0.33	0	0.46
155.6	125	0.45
247.0	200	0.52
185.8	150	0.57
124.0	100	0.78
185.8	150	0.85
-0.03	0	0.79
92.6	75	0.84
59.1	50	0.65

Z=+1, S=0.80

Model 306 O₃ nmol/mol = 1.2426 NCAS COZI O₃ nmol/mol -0.8045 nmol/mol

The above equation is valid in the amount fraction range 0-250 nmol/mol.

The new calibration coefficients of Z= +1, S=0.80 were added and a 0 and 100 ppbv check carried out.

Uncertainty is generally quoted as $\pm 3\%$ for amount fractions greater than 100 nmol/mol and 3 nmol/mol for amount fractions between 0 and 100 nmol/mol.

These uncertainties contain components arising from the uncertainty in the ozone absorption cross section, the purity of the air supply used in the calibration, any non-linearity in the analytical instrumentation, and bias in the primary standard used (based on the results of international intercomparisons).

We do recommend that you carry out calibrations at least annually to verify the stability of your calibrator.

This work was carried out in the COZI-Lab in the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry laboratories (WACL) at the University of York. The COZI-Lab exists to support the UK community and is an Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) from the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS).